

Effects of background music (Classical, Jazz, and Pop) on students' performance in Science 9 in Akle High School

Amerigo Bernardo Ramos Jr.

Abstract

Promoting skills acquisition and improving the performance of students in science is quite a challenge to teachers nowadays. It is imperative to mitigate such problems arising from lack of focus and study habits. This present study aims to determine whether the use of background music in teaching Grade 9 Science will increase the students' performance. Different background music (Classical, Jazz, and Pop) were utilized in the study among 142 students of Akle High School. A paired t-test result revealed a significant increase in their scores after the use of background music. Specifically, classical music exhibited the greatest number of gain scores which is 5.035. Though all of the genres revealed significant in increasing the students' performance, classical music was way ahead from the two other genres. As observed, pop music and jazz music gained 3.047 and 3.058, respectively.

Keywords: Background music. Students' performance. Science.

Amerigo Bernardo Ramos Jr.*

Bulacan Agricultural State College, San Ildefonso, Bulacan, Philippines
amie_ramos21@yahoo.com

***Corresponding author**

Introduction

Pursuant to the mission, vision, goals and objectives of the Department of Education, all possible means to uplift the level of education specifically the students' achievement is a must. Teachers in science nowadays experience challenges on how to keep their students' performance high. As classroom setting has developed over time, many opportunities to develop and stimulate learning became prevalent. In recent years, different researchers have studied relationship between music and academic achievements. The Mozart Effect represents a small portion of study by observing the relationship between listening to classical music and completing a spatial task (Mallory, 2012). However, this relationship is comprehensive and vague because there are different kinds of music and also, there are different areas of academic achievement.

The use of background music is one of the particular techniques that is extensively utilized to supplement and enhance student learning. Studies have shown that music plays a very important role society, and it has a strong influence on today's youth. With this information, the effort includes background music in teaching or during independent work time can become a means to promote student learning and further increase their performance in science. If the study does indeed have a positive effect, then teachers could play background music which in turn can lead to better performance of the students.

Most of the teaching styles that can be observed in the classrooms are often linguistic and mathematical. As Howard Gardner pointed out, however, these learning styles are just two among eight or more types of intelligences (Milner & Milner, 2003). Musical learning is among the Multiple Intelligences according to Gardner. Development of the musical intelligences can be greatly aided by the use of music in teaching. Furthermore, using music in the classroom will not only contribute to the development of musical abilities, but it can also enrich the learning process as well.

Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences and neuroscientific frameworks provide opportunities for instructors to consider practical applications and uses in the classroom. According to the multiple intelligences' theory, it is the teacher's responsibility to use a variety of instructional strategies to aid students' learning at school. Despite the fact that classroom teachers are less comfortable teaching music than music experts, acquiring a deeper grasp of Howard Gardner's (1983) theory of multiple intelligences might help teachers capitalize on their students' learning styles and intelligence categories.

A Bulgarian psychotherapist and physician Georgi Lozanov introduced in 1978 an unusual foreign language methodology for classroom. His method, called Suggestopedie (Suggestopedia), has been the topic of many research articles written on the use of music in the foreign language classroom. Even though psychological in nature, this method uses classical music to help make the students relax.

Lozanov (1978) pointed out the importance of whole-brain stimulation for optimal acquisition to take place and suggests that the relaxation techniques help learners tap into subconscious resources to aid acquisition and greater retention of vocabulary and language structures. Both the theories of Gardner and Lozanov are the basis for the study where background music can be a tool in developing students' performance in science.

Numerous researchers have conducted studies on the utilization of music in the classroom. However, specific studies on the use of background music and test scores in science are only few which makes this research study novel.

Maas (2013) conducted a study on the use of background music on math test performance in Algebra II. Four Algebra II courses, two regular courses, and two accelerated Algebra II classes were used in the experiment, which lasted four weeks. After the exposure to music (classical, rock, rap) four quizzes over four weeks were collected and then analyzed. Despite the fact that most students admit to not listening to classical music while completing homework, the research indicated that classical music had the strongest correlation with exam scores.

The impact of listening to music on cognitive performance was tested by Dolegui (2013). Results showed that students performed well in completing difficult academic tasks while they are being exposed to background music. There was a significant increase in their cognitive performance as well as in their test scores.

Background music plays a key role in the education process as mentioned by Behar (2005) in his research. He investigated the impact of classical music on the listening comprehension of students. Behar reported that the increased level of listening comprehension led to better grades, increased participation in class and completion of tasks. When music is played throughout the learning process, the content is retained better (Behar, 2005). The findings can be used to aid in the retention of science concepts and other scientific terms that is why the researchers will try to investigate on this area.

Integrating music in the classroom influences the performance of students. The increase in their performance was the result of many beneficial aspects of music such as increased retention, concentration and accelerated learning (Rackham, 2020). White (2007) revealed that high school students were exposed to background music and then interviewed. Then a posttest was conducted. Results revealed that most of the students reduced their stress and tensions while listening and taking the tests. The result of their posttest was significantly high compared to their pretest. Music is one technique that may be used to help children improve their academic performance (Burriss and Strickland, 2001).

Dinsmore (2003) conducted a qualitative study on fifth graders and found out that background music created a pleasant mood for the pupils. It fostered calmness and enjoyment to the class during the time of exposure. One of the teachers in the study also mentioned that music provided atmosphere which had a calming effect on the pupils. Ninety percent of the pupils interviewed stated that music helped them to stay on tasks and helped them to be focused. Activities were accomplished with ease since the pupils were focus and attentive (Dinsmore, 2003).

A calm atmosphere may provide a conducive learning environment for the students. The researchers of the present study find it substantial to incorporate background music in science class to elicit desirable mood from the students thus increasing their performance.

A slow Baroque music was used in the study of Lawrence (2001). The research revealed that English tests scores of students in Iowa State University improved significantly and increased memory retention by 26 percent. It is believed that if background music has the ability to improve language acquisition, it can also be used in learning core subjects like math and science. The present study aims to test this idea on grade 9 science subject.

A scientific research was conducted by Lerch and Anderson (2000) to further explain the effect of Mozart's music on students' performance in class. Forty-four college students were exposed to Mozart piano sonata while forty-two students waited for equivalent time in silence. Afterwards all the subjects were tested for their ability to solve puzzles and paper-folding challenges. There was a significant difference between the results of the two groups. Students who were exposed to Mozart's sonata exhibited improved performance.

The impact of Mozart's music on college students was tested by Campbell (1997). Thirty-six college students at the University of California were exposed to classical music for ten minutes before taking the intelligence test showed 9-point increase in their spatial IQ test. The present study will not only focus on classical music but also will try to investigate other genres on the performance of students in science.

Scovel (1969) termed "cerebral dominance", while Jensen (1995) called "hemispheric specialization", but both of them that are mentioned to which side of the brain was more likely to be used for different cognitive learning styles. Based on their assumptions, there are parts of the brain that are being stimulated when music is being played. The stimulation can lead to the development of the brain connections for memory storage (Jensen, 1995).

Background music promotes a happy environment, and it encourages, energizes, focuses and calms the students. Attention of the learners, desired behavior, mental set as well as creativity are all achieved when listening to music (Holland, 2009).

Research Questions

The general problem of the study is: How effective is the use of background music (Classical, Jazz and Pop) on students' performance in Science 9? Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a significant difference between the mean scores in pretest and posttest of Science 9 students with background music and without background music?
2. Which among the three background music genres (Classical, Jazz, and Pop) significantly increased the students' performance in Science 9?

Hypothesis of the Study

There is no significant difference between the mean scores in pretest and posttest of Science 9 students with background music and without background music.

Methodology

This study investigated the effectiveness of background music on the performance of students in Science 9. Moreover, the study provided an account of the impact of use of background music in classroom setup.

Type of Research

The study utilized a descriptive method of research to appraise the effects of background music on students' performance in Science 9. A Pre-test and Post-test Control and Experimental Group Design were used in the research. The interpretation and description of the data gathered were presented.

Respondents and Research Design

The subject of this study was the Grade 9 students of Akle High School located at Akle, San Ildefonso, Bulacan. The totality of the students for the School Year 2016-2017 is one hundred forty-two (142) students. From section 9-Mangga, 9-Atis and 9-Chico that consist of seventy-eight (78) female students and sixty-four (64) male students.

Sampling Method

Section 9-Mangga was the control group while sections 9-Atis and 9-Chico were the experimental groups. A total of eighty-five (85) students were exposed to the use of background music. The setup was done since the former is the pilot section while the latter are heterogeneous sections. The study investigated if there was a significant difference between the scores of the control and experimental group.

Instruments

The instrument that was used in the study was a 10-point Multiple Choice Pre- and Post-tests patterned from the Grade 9 Science Module. This was done to cover the content of the study. This also made the test valid and reliable because the questions and contents were all in line with the content and performance standards set by the Department of Education.

Background music that was utilized in the experiment were Pop Music from Billboard Charts Archive Pop Songs from 2015, Jazz Music from Billboard Smooth Jazz Songs from 2015, and Classical Music patterned from the study conducted by Maas (2013). Speakers were placed inside the classroom in front and at the back. Music was played during activity or interdisciplinary cooperative learning (ICL).

Data Collection Procedure

A pretest was administered in the beginning of the study. Both the control and experimental group answered the pre-test on the same day. After the implementation of the pre-test, the teacher played a background music during the ICL or during the activity and written quiz in Science class. The playing of music (Classical Music for the first set) continued for three weeks during non-teaching time. Thereafter, a post-test was given to the subject of the study. A background music was also played during the test taking. The scores were recorded and saved in Microsoft Excel. For the Second set (Jazz Music), the same procedure was done. A pre-test was administered on the first day followed by the playing of the background music during the activity or ICL and a written quiz on the second day. A post-test was given afterwards. The same thing is true for the last set (Pop Music).

Ethical Considerations

The researcher conducted the study in a way that the anonymity of the respondents was ensured. For confidentiality, respondents were not asked to write their names in the questionnaires. All the participants were informed that they are free to agree or refuse to participate in the study prior to the administration of the instruments.

Data Analysis

Descriptive procedure was used for analysis and interpretation. Once the data were gathered, it was analyzed using MS Excel. A paired t-test determined if there was a significant increase in the mean scores before and after the used of background music in Science 9. To be considered significant, .05 degrees of freedom was set.

Results and Discussion

All the information collected from the study have been tabulated and analyzed to have a comprehensive presentation and interpretation. Data were organized in tabular form to show significant effects of background music in the performance of grade 9 students in science.

Effect of Background Music on Students' Performance in Science 9

The effect of background music on students' performance in science 9 was tested through pretest-posttest experimental design. It is shown in Table 1 the significant difference between the performance of the students before and after their exposure to background music. Three background music genres were utilized in the study.

A mean gain score of 5.035 from the mean posttest score of 6.882 was obtained from the classical music. For the pop music, the mean posttest score of 5.235 yielded a mean gain score of 3.047. Furthermore, a mean gain score of 3.059 was attained from the mean posttest score of 4.988 from a 10-item multiple choice test given to 85 Grade 9 students.

Table 1. Pretest-posttest scores of the three music genres

	CLASSICAL			JAZZ			POP		
	PRE1 Score (10)	POST1 Score (10)	GAIN1 Score (10)	PRE2 Score (10)	POST2 Score (10)	GAIN2 Score (10)	PRE3 Score (10)	POST3 Score (10)	GAIN3 Score (10)
Mean	1.847	6.882	5.035	2.212	5.235	3.047	1.929	4.988	3.059

Table 2. Paired sample t-test for results

		Paired Differences								
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference								
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	Lower	Upper	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Pair 1	POSTCLASS - PRECLASS	5.035	1.62896	.17669	4.68394	5.38665	28.499	84	.000	
Pair 2	POSTPOP - PREPOP	3.000	1.85806	.20153	2.59923	3.40077	14.886	84	.000	
Pair 3	POSTJAZZ - PREJAZZ	3.059	1.62827	.17661	2.70761	3.41003	17.320	84	.000	

A paired sample t-test was conducted to determine whether there was a significant increase in the pretest and posttest scores of the students. As shown in Table 2, paired samples of pretest and posttest together with the background music were indicated (Pair 1 = Classical Music, Pair 2 = Pop Music, and Pair 3 = Jazz Music).

The first pair (Classical Music) t-test computed value was 0.000. Comparing it with the critical t value of 0.05, it can be determined that there was a significant increase in the posttest scores of the students.

For the second pair (Pop Music), a 0.000 computed t value was also obtained. This clearly implies that there was a significant increase in the posttest score.

The third pair (Jazz Music) indicated a 0.000 computed t value which is less than the critical t value of 0.05. This would mean that there was a significant increase in the posttest score of the students after the use of background music.

Overall implication of the test revealed that it is enough to say that the performance of the students in science significantly increased after their exposure to all the background music genres (Classical, Pop, and Jazz).

Since the computed data revealed that all the three background music genres were effective in increasing the performance of students, a graph was utilized to compare which among the genres is considered best.

Figure 1. Graphical comparison among the mean gain scores

The graph strictly represents the mean gain scores of the three background music genres utilized in the study. This is a great visual representation of the general trend of the data.

As can be noticed from the graph, classical music exhibited the greatest number of gain scores which is 5.035. It is further depicted in Table 2 that though all of the genres revealed significant in increasing the students' performance, classical music was way ahead from the two other genres. As observed, pop music and jazz music gained 3.047 and 3.058, respectively.

Conclusion and Recommendations

To determine the effect of background music (Classical, Pop, and Jazz) on students' performance in Science 9 was the goal of this study. Students were exposed to three music genres during their ICL and class activities. A pretest-posttest experimental design was utilized in the study.

Based on the results of the study, the t-test revealed that there was a significant increase in their pretest and posttest score thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This further supports the different research findings that background music can increase the performance of the students. Among the three music genres, classical music exhibited the greatest number of increases in gain score. The significance of this research on background music could be of great use to teachers and their students. Concentration and focus were very evident during the study. External noises were eliminated because of the background music being played during their activities and ICLs. Furthermore, students were able to accomplish tasks on the time allotted for them with comprehension.

Researcher recommends for future study to increase the number of participants. Increasing the size will make the study more relevant and significant. The selection of music can also be a factor to consider in future study.

References

Behar, C. (2005). *The effects of classical music on listening comprehension* (Master's thesis, Kean University). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED438589.pdf>

Burriss, K. G., & Strickland, S. J. (2001). Music and the brain in childhood development. *Childhood Education*, 78(2), 100-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00094056.2002.10522714>

Campbell, D. (1997). *The Mozart effect: Tapping the power of music to heal the body, strengthen the mind and unlock the creative spirit*. Hodder Headline Australia.

- Dinsmore, T. S. (2003). *Classroom management* (Action research, Marygrove College).
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED478771.pdf>
- Dolegui, A. S. (2013). The impact of listening to music on cognitive performance. *Inquiries Journal/Student Pulse*, 5(9).
<http://www.inquiriesjournal.com/articles/1657/the-impact-of-listening-to-music-on-cognitive-performance>
- Gardner, H. (1983). *Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligences*. Basic Books.
- Hallam, S., & Price, J. (1998). Can the use of background music improve the behavior and academic performance of children with emotional and behavioral difficulties? *British Journal of Special Education*, 25(2), 88-91.
- Holland, L. (2009). Listening to music enhances spatial-temporal reasoning: Evidence for the "Mozart effect". *Journal of Aesthetic Education*, 34(3/4), 105-148.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/3333640>
- Jensen, E. P. (2000). *Music with the brain in mind*. Corwin Press.
- Lawrence, D. L. (2001). *Using music in the classroom* (Unpublished manuscript). <https://pastpapers.ie/sites/default/files/Using%20Music%20in%20the%20Classroom.pdf>
- Lerch, D., & Anderson, T. (2000). *The Mozart Effect: A closer look*. University of Illinois. https://musicaeadoracao.com.br/recursos/arquivos/ingles/mozart_effect.htm
- Levitin, D. (2006). *This is your brain on music: The science of the brain*. Penguin Books.
- Lozanov, G. (1978). *Suggestology and outlines of suggestopedy*. Gordon and Breach Publishing Company.
- Maas, S. E. (2013). *The effect of background music on math test performance of high school students* (Master's thesis, The Honors College, Oakland University).
- Mallory, C. (2012). *The effect of music on math and science standardized test scores* (Project proposal, Worcester Polytechnic Institute).
- Milner, J., & Milner, L. (2003). *Bridging English* (3rd ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Savan, A. (1999). The effect of background music on learning. *Psychology of Music*, 27(2), 138-146.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0305735699272005>
- White, K. N. (2007). *The effects of background music in the classroom on the productivity, motivation, and behavior of fourth grade students* (Master's thesis, Columbia College).
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED522618.pdf>